

Assessment of Cost Minimization Analysis of Antimalarials in India

Mithilesh Kumar¹, Deepak Kumar², Dinesh Kumar Sah³

¹PG Student, Department of Pharmacology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

²Professor and HOD, Department of Pharmacology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

Received: 28-08-2022 / Revised: 05-09-2022 / Accepted: 20-09-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Dinesh Kumar Sah

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: To assess the cost difference of various branded and generic antimalarial drugs available in the Indian market.

Material & Methods: The present observational research was carried out in the Department of Pharmacology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India for the duration of 6 months. The minimum and maximum cost in rupees (INR) of an antimalarial drug manufactured by different pharmaceutical companies in the same dose strength was noted among all the above sources.

Results: Highest cost ratio was seen with Chloroquine 500 mg, Mefloquine 250 mg and Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 500+25 mg. Lowest cost ratio was seen with Quinine 600 mg, Chloroquine 250 mg and Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 750+37.5 mg.

Conclusion: This study reveals the need to further improve the drug price regulatory mechanism concerning antimalarials available in India to improve patient compliance and thus cure rates of malaria.

Keywords: Antimalarial drugs, Compliance, Cost ratio, Percent cost variation

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Despite being a largely preventable and treatable disease, malaria is responsible for an estimated 800,000 deaths globally each year [1], with the majority of morbidity and mortality occurring in young children in sub-Saharan Africa. In addition to its impact on health, malaria imposes a heavy economic burden on individuals [2] and entire economies [3].

The government of India launched the national malaria control programme in April 1953. Initially the programme was a

success as the number of malaria cases significantly declined. [4] The programme was changed to national malaria eradication programme in 1958. The incidence dropped further to a mere 49151 cases, with no deaths by 1961. [5]

Pharmacoeconomics involves identifying, measuring, and comparing the costs and consequences of pharmaceutical products and services. [6] There are four basic types of pharmacoeconomic studies; cost-minimization analysis, cost-effectiveness

analysis, cost-utility analysis, and cost-benefit analysis. [7, 8] Cost-minimization analysis also called cost analysis measures and compares input costs and assumes outcomes to be equivalent. Thus, in the cost-minimization analysis cost of two or more alternatives is compared without regard to outcome.

Patients from poor socioeconomic background must have access to the correct drug at the nominal price. Costly drugs can lead to economic burden which results in decreased compliance or even non-compliance. Non-compliance leads to incomplete treatment which tends to increase morbidity. There is a gross variation in the cost of different brands of same generic drugs available in India. Increase in the patient medication cost was found to be associated with decreased adherence to prescription medication. [9]

Studies conducted in past show a wide variation in cost of branded and generic versions of same drug. [10, 11]

Hence, the present study was undertaken to assess the cost difference of various branded and generic antimalarial drugs available in the Indian market.

Material & Methods:

The present observational research was carried out in the Department of Pharmacology, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India for the duration of 6 months.

Methodology

The prices of various antimalarial drugs were recorded from sources such as CIMS (Current Index of Medical Specialities). The minimum and maximum cost in rupees (INR) of an antimalarial drug manufactured by different pharmaceutical companies in the same dose strength was noted among all the above sources. The cost of 10 tablets/capsules, one bottle of syrup/drops, and that of one ampoule/vial were calculated. For artemisinin-based oral formulations cost was calculated for 3 days as per WHO and NVBDCP recommendations.

The cost ratio is defined as the ratio of the maximum cost of the drug to the minimum cost of the drug. It was calculated for all the included antimalarial drugs. This indicates the cost inflation in the prescribed drug with the same chemical compound but with different commercial brands. Cost ratio expresses the cost of drugs in proportion to the costliest and cheapest brand of the drug available in the market. Fixed drug combinations were also evaluated in the same manner as above.

Results:

Cost distribution of various oral antimalarial formulations of antimalarials were given by Table 1.

Table 1: Cost distribution of various oral antimalarial formulations

Sr. No.	Drug	Formulation	Strength	No of tablets	Minimum cost(rs)	Maximum cost(rs)
1	Chloroquine	Tablet	250 mg	10	34	56
		Tablet	500 mg	10	5.27	253
2	Amodiaquine*	Tablet	200mg	10	5	-
3	Mefloquine	Tablet	250 mg	10	14.99	678.2
		Tablet	300 mg	10	26.31	680.2
4	Quinine	Tablet	600 mg	10	78.36	133.71
		Tablet	2.5 mg	10	8.20	21.40
5	Primaquine	Tablet	7.5 mg	10	13.3	45.81
		Tablet	15 mg	10	7.8	60.29
6	Sulfadoxine-	Tablet	500 mg +	10	9.2	362

			25 mg			
7	Pyrimethamine	Tablet	750 mg + 37.5 mg	10	23.81	45.72
8	Proguanil	Tablet	100 mg	10	38.9	80.29
9	Sulfamethoxazole-	Tablet	500 mg + 25 mg	10	26.7	197.19

Among the 9 oral formulations there is a gross difference between minimum and maximum cost in most of the formulations. Highest cost ratio was seen with Chloroquine 500 mg, Mefloquine 250 mg and Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 500+25 mg. Lowest cost ratio was seen with Quinine 600 mg, Chloroquine 250 mg and Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 750+37.5 mg.

Table 2: Cost distribution of various artemisinin based oral formulations

Drug	Formulation	Strength	No of tablets	Minimum Cost (Rs)	Maximum Cost (Rs)
Arteether*	Tablet	50 mg	6	115.01	-
Artemether	Capsule	40 mg	6	107.92	130.28
	Tablet	50 mg	6	24	209.07
Artesunate	Tablet	100 mg	6	121	1200
Artemether-Lumefantrine	Tablet	80 mg + 480 mg	6	45.0	228.62
	Tablet	20 mg + 120 mg	6	52	111.3
Arteether-Lumefantrine	Tablet	80 mg + 480 mg	6	55.81	180.82
	Tablet	20 mg + 120 mg	6	65.92	77.72
Artesunate Sulfadoxine Pyrimethamine	Tablet	100 mg + 500	3	14.22	190
	Tablet	mg + 25 mg	3	182.12	300
		200 mg + 750 mg +25 mg			
Artesunate-Amodiaquine*	Tablet	100 mg + 300 mg	6	117.92	-
Artesunate Mefloquine	Tablet	100 mg + 200 mg	6	298.72	480
Arterolane-Piperaquine*	Tablet	150 mg + 750	3	197	-
	Tablet	mg 37.5 mg + 187.5 mg	3	78	-

Table 2 Shows cost distribution of various artemisinin based oral formulations. Among the 14 artemisinin based oral formulations there is a significant difference between minimum and maximum cost in most of the formulations.

Cost ratio of various artemisinin based oral formulations were given by Table 3.

Table 3: Percentage of cost variation of various artemisinin based oral formulations

Drug	Strength	Percentage of cost variation
Arteether	50 mg	-
Artemether	40 mg	20.62 %
Artesunate	50 mg	769.27 %

	100 mg	900.21 %
Artemether-Lumefantrine	80 mg + 480 mg 20 mg + 120 mg	385.72 % 114.81 %
Arteether Lumefantrine	80 mg + 480 mg 20 mg + 120 mg	230.42 % 19.80 %
Artesunate Sulfadoxine- Pyrimethamine	100 mg + 500 mg + 25 mg 200 mg + 750 mg + 25 mg	1168.91 % 61.62 %
Artesunate-Amodiaquine	100 mg + 300 mg	-
Artesunate-Mefloquine	100 mg + 200 mg	60.55 %
Arterolane-Piperaquine 14	150 mg + 750 mg 37.5 mg + 187.5 mg	- -

Highest cost ratio was seen with Artesunate - Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 100+500+25 mg, Artesunate 100 mg and Artesunate 50 mg. Lowest cost ratio was seen with Artemether 40 mg, Arteether – Lumefantrine 20+120 mg, Artesunate - Sulfadoxine – Pyrimethamine 200+750+25 mg and Artesunate – Mefloquine 100+200 mg.

Percentage of cost variation of various parenteral antimalarial formulations is given in Table 4 respectively. Highest percentage of cost variation was seen with Arteether 150 mg, Quinine 300 mg and Quinine 600 mg. Lowest percentage of cost variation was seen with Artesunate 120 mg, Artemether 80 mg and Artesunate 60 mg.

Table 4: Percentage of cost variation of various parenteral antimalarial formulations

Drug	Strength	Percentage of cost variation
Chloroquine	40mg	156.82 %
Quinine	300 mg	1260.62%
	600 mg	1052.39 %
	75 mg	822.30 %
Arteether	120 mg	-
	150 mg	2372.8 %
Artemether	80 mg	37.73 %
Artesunate	60 mg	135.83 %
	120 mg	11.74 %
Alpha- Beta Arteether	150 mg	280.46 %

Discussion:

People living in developing countries pay heavy cost of medicines. In India, more than 80% health financing is borne by patients. [12-14] The situation becomes more complex due to the presence of number of brands with variety of names and prices. [15]

The primary studies of costing data identified estimated the costs of single interventions in the absence of other anti-malaria interventions, with the exception

of a study by Picard et al [16]. However estimates of the costs and cost-effectiveness of combined interventions were possible in model-based studies [17, 18].

Anti-malaria interventions will increasingly be deployed as part of wider health system strengthening packages leading to possible economies of scope: witness the IPTi studies by Manzi et al [19] where the cost of a course of intermittent preventive treatment was

reduced due to its administration alongside the already existing (and therefore not an additional financial cost) Expanded Programme on Immunization.

India has a high incidence of malaria because of unstable malaria transmission with increased intensity of transmission during rains and poor or absent immunity to malarial parasite among the Indian population. [20, 21] Given the magnitude of malaria in our country antimalarial drugs should be made available at prices which will not be an economic burden on the largely poor population of our country. In India many pharmaceutical companies sell a drug in different generic and brand names and this has led to wide variation in the price of generic and branded formulation of these drugs.

The cost-effectiveness literature is also lacking in the evaluation of combined malaria interventions. Apart from the studies by Akhavan et al [22] and Mills [23] on the evaluation of national or district level malaria control programmes, only one study considers simultaneously deployed interventions.

An expensive brand can cost a patient more than ten times the price of a cheaper brand of the same drug. This reflects a serious concern in the context of India where 50-90% of cost of medicines are still borne by the patient themselves. This high cost of purchasing medicines is a significant factor leading to poor compliance. [24-25] Clinician's false belief of effectiveness or superiority of branded drugs over generic drugs often results in prescription of costly drugs, when cheaper alternatives are readily available.

A significant price variation among injectable antimalarial for example there is significant cost ratio and cost variation of Artemether injection 150mg/2ml (cost ratio = 16.96 and % cost variation = 1596). Injectable antimalarials are often the choice of drug when dealing with critically

ill malaria patients specially when suffering from complicated malaria. So, such significant price variation creates economic burden on poor patients. This often leads to non-compliance or abrupt cessation of treatment which adds on the morbidity and mortality due to malaria.

The treating physician should be made aware of the cheapest drug available among the various brands so that the patient bears lesser burden of treatment cost. Costs of drug are controlled by the drug cost control order 2013 (DPCO). [26]

In a study in coastal and western Kenya Ngugi et al [27] evaluated the cost to employers of distributing ITNs to employees to be \$15.80 per net delivered in 2002 prices. 48% of the costs were classified as tradable and 52% as non-tradable. The exchange rates were 1 USD = 78 KSH in 2002 and 1 USD = 82 KSH in 2009.

Medication compliance refers to the extent of conformity to treatment recommendation with respect to the timing, dosage, frequency and duration of a prescribed medicine. It can also be described as the degree to which a patient correctly follows medical advice. Other factors contributing to patient's non-compliance include: drug formulation, improvement of symptoms, frequent dosing, side effects of drugs, etc. [7, 8, 28]

Conclusion:

This study reveals the need to further improve the drug price regulatory mechanism concerning antimalarials available in India to improve patient compliance and thus cure rates of malaria.

References:

1. WHO: World Malaria Report - 2010 Geneva: WHO.
2. Chima RI, Goodman CA, Mills A: The economic impact of malaria in Africa: a critical review of the evidence. Health Policy 2003; 63:17-36.

3. Sachs J, Malaney P: The economic and social burden of malaria. *Nature* 2002; 415:680-685.
4. PB Health. National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme. Available at <http://pbhealth.gov.in/pdf/malaria.pdf>.
5. Dash AP, Valecha N, Anvikar AR, Umar A. Malaria in India: challenges and opportunities. *J Biosci.* 2008; 33:5 83-92.
6. Rascati K. Essentials of pharmacoeconomics. In: 2nd Edn. vol. 28. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer Health/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2014; 1 – 8.
7. Prasad SN, Vedavathi H. Pharmacoeconomic study of antipsychotic drugs in India. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol.* 2017;6(2):377–82.
8. Walker BR, Colledge NR, Ralston S, Penman ID, Britton R. Davidson's principles and practice of medicine. In: 22nd Edn.. vol. 13. New York: Churchill Livingstone/Elsevier; 2014; 353–8.
9. Eaddy MT, Cook CL, O'Day K, Burch SP, Cantrell CR. How patient cost-sharing trends affect adherence and outcomes: a literature review. *PT.* 2012; 37:45-55.
10. Das SC, Mandal M, Mandal SC. A critical study on availability and price variation between different brands: impact on access to medicines. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2007;69(1):160-3.
11. Chawan VS, Gawand KV, Badwane SV. Cost analysis of oral hypolipidemic agents available in India. *Int J Basic Pharmacol.* 2014;3: 954-7.
12. Thomas M. Rational drug use and essential drug concept. In: Parthasarathi G, Nyfort Hasen K, Editors. *A Textbook of Clinical Pharmacy Practice.* 1st Ed. Himayat Nagar, Hyderabad: Orient Longman; 2004:72 3.
13. Creese A, Kotwani A, Kutzin J, Pillay A. Evaluating pharmaceuticals for health policy in low and middle-income country settings. In: Freemantle N, Hill S, eds. *Evaluating pharmaceuticals for health policy and reimbursement.* Massachusetts, USA: Blackwell Publication; (in collaboration with WHO Geneva); 2004:227-243.
14. Hill S, eds. *Evaluating pharmaceuticals for health policy and reimbursement.* Massachusetts, USA: Blackwell Publication; (in collaboration with WHO Geneva); 2004:227-243.
15. Mahal A, Karan A, Engelgau M. *The Economic Implications of Non-Communicable Disease for India.* Washington, DC: World Bank.2010. Available at <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/HEALTHNUTRITIONANDPOPULATION/Resources/281627-1095698140167/EconomicImplicationsofNCDforIndia.pdf>.
16. Picard J, Aikins M, Alonso PL, Schellenberg J, Greenwood BM, Mills A: A malaria control trial using insecticide-treated bed nets and targeted chemoprophylaxis in a rural area of The Gambia, West-Africa. 8. Cost-effectiveness of bed net impregnation alone or combined with chemoprophylaxis in preventing mortality and morbidity from malaria in Gambian children. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg* 1993; 87:53-57.
17. Goodman CA, Coleman PG, Mills AJ: Cost-effectiveness of malaria control in sub-Saharan Africa. *Lancet* 1999, 354:378-385
18. Morel CM, Lauer JA, Evans DB: Achieving the millennium development goals for health - Cost effectiveness analysis of strategies to combat malaria in developing countries. *BM J* 2005; 331:1299-130 2B.
19. Manzi F, Hutton G, Schellenberg J, Tanner M, Alonso P, Mshinda H, Schellenberg D: From strategy development to routine implementation: the cost of Intermittent Preventive Treatment in Infants for malaria control. *Bmc Health Services Research* 2008; 8.
20. Tripathi KD. *Essentials of medical pharmacology.* In: and others, editor.

- 8th Edn. vol. 61. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers (P), Ltd; 2018: 873–92.
21. Brunton LL, Knollmann BC, Hilal-Dandan R. Gilman's the pharmacological basis of therapeutics. In: 13th Edn.. vol. 53. New York: Mc Graw Hill Medical; 2018: 969–82.
 22. Akhavan D, Musgrove P, Abrantes A, Gusmao RD: Cost-effective malaria control in Brazil - Cost-effectiveness of a Malaria Control Program in the Amazon Basin of Brazil, 1988-1996. Soc Sci Med 1999; 49:1385-1399.
 23. Mills A: Is malaria control a priority? Evidence from Nepal. Health Econ 1993; 2: 333-347.
 24. Kasper DL. Harrison's principles of internal medicine. In: 19th Edn. vol. 248. New York: McGraw Hill Education; 2015; 1368–84.
 25. Kumar PJ, Clark M. Kumar & Clark's clinical medicine. In: and others, editor. 8th Edn.. vol. 4. Edinburgh: Saunders, Elsevier; 2012; 143–6.
 26. Drug Cost Control Order, 2013, Government of India. Available at <http://www.nppaindia.nic.in/DPCO2013.pdf>.
 27. Ngugi IK, Chiguzo AN, Guyatt HL: A cost analysis of the employer-based bednet programme in Coastal and Western Kenya. Health Policy and Planning 2004; 19:111-119.
 28. Balde A. K., A T. J., MD S., TM B., A, M., K B. A., & S, D. Hyperopia in young people: risk factors and prognosis at the CADES/O of the Donka National Hospital Guinea. Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences, 2022; 5(8); 2135–2144.